

The Internet and the Things

Rocco Gagliardi

Defense Department, scip AG
roga@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Keywords: Bluetooth, Cisco, Flash, Framework, GitHub, Google, HTML, HTTP, IBM, Identity

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2015 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150813> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Imagine a *sex toy* [1] talking with an application on the phone, adjusting mechanical parameters in accordance with the personal profile stored, or based on FB Likes, or using a *playlist* of mechanical movements, controlled sounds, lights, and smells, or even a json stream of parameters from a remote controlled application (by another sex toy?) on another continent. Today, reading *The velvet underground* [2] is like reading about Brontosaurus (not *Brontobytes* [3] ... that's the future again). *Teledildonics* [4] were described by Isaac Asimov, in his 1957 novel *The Naked Sun* [5] the planet *Solaria* [6] practiced it.

This may be a vision (aside the more conventional *refrigerator* [7], messaging about the milk expiration date) of how things may interact over internet, and may become one of the real driving force for development and refinement of technologies still in its infancy.

The Internet is approaching the second revolution, becoming the Internet 2.0. Sex is approaching the 4th revolution, becoming Sex 4.0: we are light-years behind.

Many technologies are converging, new computation models (not just quantum computing, but as example the HP memristor based devices (*The Machine* [8]), which promises, with the new memory paradigm, a more efficient computing), power efficient devices and transmission protocols, new types of batteries, OTA recharging and much more.

Powerful computers in our pockets, glasses to augment our reality, small sensors to measure position, acceleration, pulse, pressure, humidity and a lot of other environmental parameters. All these things are going to communicate with a central entity or with the neighbouring device that collects data, interprets it and reacts in some manner. The exponential growth of sensors, physical and virtual, will provide smart machines with more *perception* and context

of the physical world; every one of these things may become *autonomous*, acting and reacting to its neighbour's needs or capability, becoming a distributed cognitive (dare I say intelligent?) system.

3. What is the Internet of Things?

My generation (I was born in the year of the Man on the Moon, Internet and El Primero) has been illuminated by only one Sun, and our mantra was *The Network is The Computer*. The Internet is defined more by what you can do than what it does.

The Internet of Things (IoT) suffers from similar confusion. The big information players are pushing out vision statements trying to define the IoT:

- Cisco calls it the *Internet of Everything* and says it will be the *latest wave of the Internet—connecting physical objects... to provide better safety, comfort and efficiency*.
- IBM describes it as *a completely new world-wide Web, one comprised of the messages that digitally empowered devices would send to one another. It is the same Internet, but not the same Web*.
- General Electric's *Industrial Internet* is perhaps the most exciting vision because it directly envisions new applications. At GE, the industrial Internet represents *the convergence of machine and intelligent data... to create brilliant machines*.

Where is the IoT? Where are all these devices? They are part of the fabric of everyday life. In fact, you own many of them! Recent cars use more than 100 processors. Smart devices pervade industrial systems, hospitals, houses, transportation systems, and more. Today, these systems are weakly connected, but that will quickly change. By 2020, we will have around 33 billions (+/-25%) inter-connected devices! Not the proportion of *Solaria* (10K robots per human), but a huge number, growing at huge rate.

This spectacular prospective is an evolution of decades of tests and failures, unstable and buggy hardware and software. But this ecosystem evolves (giving our genes another *kind of armor* [9], using Dawkins's words) and in this constellation we found some old friends that are foundations (with all the known and unknown problems) of this new world, exposing their weakness to a growing audience.

Recalling the initial example, the idea is pretty easy: at least two people want to interact, regardless from their location.

The implementation is a little bit harder: we need power sources, step motors, Bluetooth sender/receiver, application servers, WIFI APs, Internet access, a lot of protocols for the communication of the devices status and for the commands to act/react, GUIs and APIs and much more.

That's just for our use-case; now think of the thousands of possible use cases. There are a lot of things going on around us.

4. How it (Should) Work

What are the basic requirements of a framework?

- Devices must communicate with each other (D2D).
- Device data must be collected and sent to the server infrastructure (D2S).
- That server infrastructure has to
 - share device data (S2S)
 - providing it back to devices
 - providing it to analysis programs
 - providing it to people
- Additionally, devices must be stable, function for a long period of time with small amount of power, and provide a wide range of features.

We could simply depict a model with the following actors:

Source	Transport	Network	Connection	Host
Sensors	Short-range	Identity Mgmt	Internet	Servers
Smart Devices	Medium-Range	Information	PtP	Corp.Network
Gateways	Long-range	-	Other	Acc.Control
-	Non-wireless	-	-	-

5. Overview

There are plenty of technologies involved in the IoT, hard and soft. The following high level overview might seem a bit confusing – remember: we are talking about a well defined thing named *Internet of Everything*, =I!Web (*Same internet, not same Web, Industrial Internet ...*) – but cites only a small number of all the acronyms existing under the IoT umbrella.

These protocols are widely adopted and have many implementations, claim to be real-time and connect thousands of devices. And it's true, depending on how you define *real time, things, and devices*.

The OSI model [10] should give a birds-eye view of what we are talking about.

Figure: Internet of Things OSI Model

[11]

5.1. PHY/MAC Layer

The PHY/MAC Layer contains basic networking hardware transmission technologies. Due to the plethora of available hardware technologies with widely varying characteristics, this is perhaps the most complex layer.

Key protocols players in this layer:

- *IEEE 802.15.4* [12] It is the basis for the ZigBee, ISA100.11a, WirelessHART, and MiWi specifications, each of which further extends the standard by developing the upper layers which are not defined in IEEE 802.15.4. Alternatively, it can be used with 6LoWPAN and standard Internet protocols to build a wireless embedded Internet.
- *NFC* [13] Based on the standard ISO/IEC 18092:2004, using inductive coupled devices at a center frequency of 13.56 MHz. The data rate is up to 424 kbps and the range is with a few meters short compared to the wireless sensor networks.
- *RFID* [14] Radio-Frequency Identification is the wireless use of electromagnetic fields to transfer data, for the purposes of automatically identifying and tracking tags attached to objects.
- *Bluetooth* [15] is a wireless technology standard for exchanging data over short distances. Invented by telecom vendor Ericsson in 1994, it was originally conceived as a wireless alternative to RS-232 data cables. It can connect several devices, overcoming problems of synchronization.
- *WiFi* [16] is a local area wireless computer networking technology that allows electronic devices to network.
- *Ethernet* [17] is a family of computer networking technologies for local and metropolitan area networks.
- *WiMax* [18] Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access is a wireless communications standard designed to provide 30 to 40 megabit-per-second data rates, with the 2011 update providing up to 1 Gbit/s for fixed stations.

Others: *WirelessHart* [19], *DigiMesh* [20], *ISA100.11a* [21], *ANT* [22], *EnOcean* [23], *Dash7* [24], *Thread* [25], *Weightless* [26]

5.2. Network Connectivity Layer / Transport Layer

- *IPv6* [27] IPv6, is an Internet Layer protocol for packet-switched internetworking and provides end-to-end datagram transmission across multiple IP networks.
- *6LoWPAN* [28] 6LoWPAN is a acronym of IPv6 over Low power Wireless Personal Area Networks. It is an adaption layer for IPv6 over IEEE802.15.4 links. This protocol operates only in the 2.4 GHz frequency range with 250 kbps transfer rate.
- *UDP* [29]
- *DTLS* [30] The DTLS protocol provides communications privacy for datagram protocols. The protocol allows client/server applications to communicate in a way that is designed to prevent eavesdropping, tampering, or message forgery. The DTLS protocol is based on the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol and provides equivalent security guarantees.

Others: *NanoIP* [31], *uIP* [32]

5.3. Application Layer

- *CoAP* [33] CoAP is an application layer protocol that is intended for use in resource-constrained internet devices, such as WSN nodes. CoAP is designed to easily translate to HTTP for simplified integration with the web.
- *MQTT* [34] The MQTT protocol enables a publish/subscribe messaging model in an extremely lightweight way. It is useful for connections with remote locations where a small code footprint is required and/or network bandwidth is at a premium.
- *XMPP* [35] An open technology for real-time communication, which powers a wide range of applications including instant messaging, presence, multi-party chat, voice and video calls, collaboration, lightweight middleware, content syndication, and generalized routing of XML data.
- *AMQP* [36] An open standard application layer protocol for message-oriented middleware. The defining features of AMQP are message orientation, queuing, routing (including point-to-point and publish-and-subscribe), reliability and security.

Others: *SMCP* [37], *ROLL* [38], *Mihini/M3DA* [39], *DDS* [40], *LLAP* [41], *LWM2M* [42], *SSI* [43], *IOTDB* [44], *Reactive Streams* [45], *SensorML* [46], *Semantic Sensor Net Ontology* [47], *IPSO Application Framework* [48], *OMA LightweightM2M v1.0* [49], *Wolfram Language – Connected Devices* [50], *Content-Centric Networking* [51], *Telehash* [52], *Time Synchronized Mesh Protocol* [53]

5.4. ZigBee

ZigBee [54] is a low-cost, low-power, wireless star, tree and generic mesh network standard (based on an IEEE 802.15.4 for low-rate WPANs) targeted at wide development of long battery life devices in wireless control and monitoring applications. The specification includes four additional key components:

1. Network layer
2. Application layer
3. ZigBee device objects (ZDOs)
4. Manufacturer-defined application objects that allow for customization and favor total integration.

Zigbee devices have low latency, which further reduces average current and are typically integrated with radios and with microcontrollers, and have between 60 and 256 KB flash memory. Typically used in low data rate applications that require long battery life and secure networking, has a defined rate of 250 kbit/s, best suited for intermittent data transmissions from a sensor or input device.

ZigBee is the only open, global wireless standard to provide the foundation for the Internet of Things by enabling simple and smart objects to work together, improving comfort and efficiency in everyday life.

6. The IoT Operating Systems

The IoT refers to a wide range of devices, ranging from the 8-bit, tiny memory, low power up to the powerful smartphones. Traditional OSES or specialized firmware for sensors are both unable to fulfill the basic requirement of these new device classes.

An OS for the IoT should have:

- Support for heterogeneous Hardware: small memory requirement, low power CPU, should run without MMU/FPU
- Autonomy: energy efficient (to run on battery for a long time), should communicate using well known protocols, should be reliable.
- Programmability: should be possible to develop with a well known, high level language

Refer to *Operating Systems for the IoT – Goals, Challenges, and Solutions* [55] for a discussion about the OS for the IoT.

The most interesting Operating System for the IoT devices:

- *RIOT OS* [56] It is based on a microkernel and designed for: energy efficiency, hardware independent development, a high degree of modularity. Very small (~1.5kb/5kb) is Real-Time, Multi-Threading, has C/C++ support.
- *Tiny OS* [57] TinyOS is an open source, BSD-licensed operating system designed for low-power wireless devices, such as those used in sensor networks, ubiquitous computing, personal area networks, smart buildings, and smart meters.
- *Contiki* [58] Contiki is an open source operating system for the Internet of Things. Contiki connects tiny low-cost, low-power microcontrollers to the Internet.

Others: *Brillo* [59], *Mantis* [60], *Nano-RK* [61], *LiteOS* [62], *FreeRTOS* [63], *Thingsquare Mist* [64], *Saphire* [65]

7. Visual Programming Tools

The IoT will be everywhere, from the refrigerator to the shoe sole. A lot of different people will be faced with the programming of such devices, and not all have C++ experience. New easy and intuitive interface are required, and here some projects:

- *Open Source Node-RED* [66] is a tool for wiring together hardware devices, APIs and online services in new and interesting ways.
- *NETLab Toolkit* [67] NTK (the NETLab Toolkit) is an authoring system for those who want to design and build tangible IoT projects. With a simple drag and drop interface, connect sensors, actuators, media and networks with the smart widgets.

8. Natural Language

Input interfaces are fundamental for a human-machine interaction. The IoT devices are very small, with tiny or inexistent screen, without keyboards or even buttons. Interacting in a *Natural Language* [68] with these devices is the only practicable way.

Apart from Siri or Google Search, there are other services that translate the human language to program actions: *Wit.AI* [69] enables not only the maker of the device, but also its ecosystem of developers, to build their must-have voice interface.

9. Summary

IoT [70] will have a huge *impact* [71] on our lives, in a relative small period of time. New and old technologies are mixing to make the IoT work, things are moving fast. Our challenge is to remain technologically updated and explore the possibilities and problems these new things will give us.

10. Bibliography:

- *Exploring the Protocols of IoT* [72]
- *ISO, IoT Preliminary Report 2014* [73]
- *Internet-of-Things Architecture* [74]
- *Machine-to-Machine Communication* [75]
- *Smart Energy Profile (SEP) 2.0 Uncovered* [76]
- *Understanding the Internet of Things* [77]
- *Gartner Says the Internet of Things Will Transform the Data Center* [78]

11. External Links

- [1] <http://www.wired.com/2015/05/new-sex-toys-sync-virtual-reality-porn/>
- [2] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Velvet_Underground_%28book%29
- [3] <http://www.whatsabyte.com/>
- [4] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teledildonics>
- [5] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Naked_Sun
- [6] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solaria>
- [7] <http://www.forbes.com/sites/benkepess/2015/06/16/ge-delivers-the-iot-refidgerator-at-last-those-long-promised-robotic-cars-are-here-not-quite/>
- [8] <http://www.hpl.hp.com/research/systems-research/themachine/>

- [9] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Selfish_Gene
- [10] <http://asciiflow.com/>
- [11] https://www.scip.ch/labs/images/internet_of_things_os_i_model.png
- [12] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IEEE_802.15.4
- [13] <http://www.nfc-forum.org/home/>
- [14] <http://www.rfidjournal.com/articles/view?1335>
- [15] <http://www.bluetooth.com/Pages/Bluetooth-Home.aspx>
- [16] <http://www.wi-fi.org/>
- [17] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ethernet>
- [18] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/WiMAX>
- [19] http://www.hartcomm.org/protocol/wihart/wireless_technology.html
- [20] <http://www.digi.com/technology/digimesh/>
- [21] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISA100.11a>
- [22] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ANT_%28network%29
- [23] <http://www.enocean.com/en/home/>
- [24] <http://www.dash7.org/>
- [25] <http://www.threadgroup.org/About.aspx>
- [26] <http://www.weightless.org/>
- [27] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPv6>
- [28] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/6LoWPAN>
- [29] <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc768>
- [30] <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc4347>
- [31] <http://www.cwc.oulu.fi/nanoip/>
- [32] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/UIP_%28micro_IP%29
- [33] <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-core-coap/>
- [34] <http://mqtt.org/>
- [35] <http://xmpp.org>
- [36] <http://www.amqp.org/>
- [37] <https://github.com/darconeous/smcp/tree/smcp-0.6>
- [38] <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/roll/>
- [39] http://wiki.eclipse.org/Mihini/M3DA_Specification
- [40] <http://portals.omg.org/dds/>
- [41] <http://openkontrol.org/llap/index.php/openkontrol/69-LLAP%20-%20Lightweight%20Local%20Automation%20Protocol>
- [42] <http://yucianga.info/?p=786>
- [43] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simple_Sensor_Interface_protocol
- [44] <http://iotdb.org/>
- [45] <http://www.reactive-streams.org/>
- [46] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SensorML>
- [47] http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/ssn/wiki/Semantic_Sensor_Net_Ontology
- [48] <http://www.ipso-alliance.org/wp-content/media/draft-ipso-app-framework-04.pdf>
- [49] http://technical.openmobilealliance.org/Technical/release_program/lightweightM2M_v1_0.aspx
- [50] <http://reference.wolfram.com/language/guide/ConnectingToDevices.html>
- [51] <http://www.ccnx.org/>
- [52] <http://telehash.org/>
- [53] <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/TSMP>
- [54] <http://www.zigbee.org/>
- [55] http://www.researchgate.net/publication/236883971_Operating_Systems_for_the_IoT_Goals_Challenges_and_Solutions
- [56] <http://www.riot-os.org/>
- [57] <http://www.tinyos.net/>
- [58] <http://www.contiki-os.org/>
- [59] <https://developers.google.com/brillo/?hl=en>
- [60] <http://mantisos.org/index/tiki-index.php.html>

- [61] <http://www.nanork.org/>
- [62] <http://www.liteos.net/>
- [63] <http://www.freertos.org/>
- [64] <http://thingsquare.com/mist/>
- [65] <http://sapphireos.com/#platform>
- [66] <http://nodered.org/>
- [67] <http://www.netlabtoolkit.org/>
- [68] <http://www.wired.com/2014/02/growing-importance-natural-language-processing/>
- [69] <https://wit.ai/>
- [70] http://www.cisco.com/web/solutions/trends/iot/introduction_to_IoT_november.pdf
- [71] <http://www.bcs.org/upload/pdf/societal-impact-report-feb13.pdf>
- [72] <https://www.sparkfun.com/news/1705>
- [73] http://www.iso.org/iso/big_data_report-jtc1.pdf
- [74] <http://www.iot-a.eu/arm/d1.2>
- [75] <http://www.onem2m.org/>
- [76] http://www.eetimes.com/document.asp?doc_id=1279156
- [77] http://www.gsma.com/connectedliving/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/cl_iot_wp_07_14.pdf title="IoT
- [78] <http://www.gartner.com/newsroom/id/2684616>